

Blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity: Taking Control of Identity in Federated Learning

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ABSTRACT Blockchain network (BCN)-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) has emerged lately as an identity and access management framework that is based on Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and allows users to control their own data. Federated Learning (FL), on the other hand, provides a collaborative framework to update Machine Learning (ML) models without relying explicitly on data exchange between the users. This paper investigates identity management and authentication for vehicle users in the context of FL. We propose a novel approach based on blockchain-based SSI, which focuses on maintaining the authenticity and integrity of vehicle users' identities and data exchanged between the users and the aggregation server during the execution of the FL iterations. A primary objective of this paper is to achieve shorter durations for credential operations in an FL setting as the system size scales out. Integrating BCN-based SSI into the FL framework addresses several critical FL challenges, ensuring enhanced system security and operational integrity. This synergy of BCN-based SSI with federated learning enables robust identity verification providing a solution to fundamental trustworthiness issues in FL without sacrificing the benefits of decentralized data control, improving both the performance and reliability of the FL system. Experimental results suggest that the proposed FL-based system, together with credential management on a blockchain platform, has the potential to significantly improve data integrity and ensure the authentication of users. More specifically, the results of the FL system demonstrate that it takes longer (on the order of a hundred seconds) as the number of rounds and clients increase, while the implemented Decentralized Identifier (DID) system relying on BCN-based SSI has dramatically shorter dedicated time for completing credential operations.

INDEX TERMS Self-sovereign Identity, Blockchain, Federated Learning, Authentication, Security.

I. Introduction

Web 3.0 has received increasing attention, which provides decentralized applications and advanced security features [1]. This paradigm shift is underpinned by a myriad of emergent technologies, including Blockchain Networks (BCNs), smart contracts, Artificial Intelligence (AI), distributed commu-

nication protocols, and cryptographic techniques. As Web 3.0 takes center stage, a plethora of novel applications emerge, promising unprecedented diversity and utility. Yet, among this wave of progress, challenges continue to loom large, overshadowing the security and trustworthiness of decentralized networks. One such challenge lies in the in-

tegration of AI into the fabric of emerging Web 3.0 applications [2]. As AI applications become ubiquitous, it must adapt to the imperatives of privacy preservation and value sharing among participants, safeguarding the integrity of decentralized ecosystems. Traditional approaches to security, such as Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), face scrutiny in decentralized environments. Moreover, services can be disrupted in case Centralized Authority (CA) fails or incurs an error (which can be catastrophic for mission-critical vehicle services). To address these concerns, innovative solutions like Distributed Identity Management (DIM) have emerged, epitomized by platforms like Hyperledger Indy¹. By leveraging selective disclosure and Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs), DIM solutions instill trust without relying on the centralized constructs of PKI. For example, the digital evidence that a vehicle user is eligible to participate in Federated Learning (FL) process (e.g., training a model for image recognition) can be validated without providing additional personal information such as naming or identification numbers.

DIM solutions rely on Decentralized Identifier (DID) and Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI). DID is akin to a username and password pair, supported by public/private key pairs, and recorded in a BCN by a person, organization, or device. DID consists of a unique identifier (produced by owners) and an associated DID document. DID documents, typically expressed using JSON-LD, contain at least one public key (created by the owner), a list of DID authentication methods, services, and 'verifiable claims.' Verifiable claims support two roles: (i) *claim holders* (entities that receive and hold claims) and (ii) *verifiers* (entities that verify claims about a subject). Each entity can have multiple DIDs and a different DID for each service, ensuring entities remain uncorrelated across services. SSI ensures individuals can control their data.

DIM is still a key open issue [3], and a solution based on Distributed Ledger Technologys (DLTs) can be very powerful if some of the key issues (e.g., power, network stability, some form of security attack, etc.) can be properly addressed [4]. One type of DLT is blockchain, and the authors in [5] address security concerns and support identity management with blockchain for metaverses consisting of interconnected sub-metaverses. A Multi-Identifier Network (MIN) architecture using high-performance blockchain that aims to realise sovereign equality in cyberspace by combining legal theory with network technology to establish co-governance at the technical level is explored in [6]. On the other hand, blockchain as a subgroup of distributed systems faces the CAP (Consistency, Availability, and Partition) trilemma, which includes security, scalability and decentralization. To address it, the paper in [7] proposes a general trilemma and introduces GBT-CHAIN, a framework for permissioned blockchains that successfully achieves consistency, scalability, and partition tolerance without com-

promise by combining consensus algorithms and physical topology. For distributed consortia, a new consensus algorithm Proof of Vote (POV), in which the consortium partners coordinate distributed nodes for decentralized arbitration is given in [8]). A BCN-based SSI in a FL architecture can help overcome some of limitations mentioned above. The paper in [9] presents various options to consider for BCN-based SSI architectures. BCN-based mechanisms such as reputation systems and proof-of-work can help build trust between FL participants. There exist many approaches utilizing FL, BCNs, smart contracts, Interplanetary File System (IPFS), SSI ledger, and a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) communication channel for secure, private and efficient data sharing, trust establishment and authentication purposes. In particular, FL has been used with BCNs to provide trust and privacy in several previous works, e.g., in [10] for edge networks, in [11] for applications that integrate FL with BCN for Vehicular Ad Hoc Network (VANET), in [12] for autonomous vehicles, in [13] for Internet of Things (IoT) systems and in [14] for industry 4.0. However, classical FL can suffer from various attacks including adversarial attacks, authentication, and model inversion attacks which need to be enhanced. In the context of identity management and authentication, the authors in [15] provide an identity management and authentication scheme for edge devices utilizing FL.

All of the above methods offer various approaches to identity management, either as standalone solutions or in combination with other techniques (such as FL or differential privacy approaches). However, there is a lack of SSI platform that can provide integrity and authentication simultaneously while keeping the data private (e.g., by relying on techniques such as FL). Therefore, in this paper, we propose a new architecture and a design approach based on blockchain-based SSI during FL process so that we can ensure authentication and integrity of vehicle users' identity and their data, all simultaneously. Additionally, we propose a secure registration and authentication mechanism to verify the legitimacy of FL workers and FL server to eliminate unauthorized malicious workers in the FL process. The security of the proposed authentication mechanism is verified both informally and formally, employing methods such as ROR logic, Scyther, and the AVISPA tool. To demonstrate the effectiveness of the designed protocol, a comparative analysis is conducted, assessing security features, computational complexity, communication overhead, storage requirements, and energy consumption costs. For validations, we implemented a container-based Hyperledger Indy as a DID system on OpenStack, with four DID container nodes created as DID issuers and an FL system with aggregation server and FL clients running in one Docker container using FastAPI as the REST Application Programming Interface (API). Our experiments result demonstrate valuable insights into the performance of the combined FL and DID system in terms of time and accuracy to enhance the security and efficiency of the system. The results show that the implemented DID

¹Online: <https://www.hyperledger.org/use/hyperledger-indy>, Available: January 2023.

system has a shorter duration for credential operations, while the FL system takes longer as the number of rounds and clients increases. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II gives an outline of how SSI can be applied in FL. Section III presents proposed BCN-based SSI architecture for FL. Section IV contains details on the registration and authentication phases. Section V provides the informal and formal security verification using ROR logic, Scyther and AVISPA tools. Section VI contains the experimental results and numerical comparisons and gives the performance evaluation of the security features and the cost evaluation. Section VII discusses the obtained results in terms of security features and potential privacy implications. Finally, Section VIII presents the paper’s conclusions.

II. Background on SSI for FL

In this section, we propose an FL setup that blends machine learning, network security, and distributed computing to achieve privacy-preserving, scalable, and efficient model training across numerous devices. Section II.A describes the fundamental principles of how SSI operates within the context of FL, including the establishment of trust between clients and the aggregation server. Section II.B explains the specifics of the neural network model used in the FL phases.

FL enables multiple clients (e.g. smartphones or vehicles) to learn a prediction model together, with all training data remaining on the device. This decouples the machine learning capability from the need to store the data in the cloud. FL process involves several key components in its implementation, particularly in a scenario with distributed clients (like vehicles in a vehicular network) and a central FL aggregation server. In a typical K -client FL implementation, with each client having n_k data samples (in a data set $\mathcal{D}_k = \{x_i^k\}$), the aggregation server sends the current model parameters w_t to a fraction C of the clients (as part of Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm). Each client computes their local gradient $g_k = \nabla F_k(w_t)$ where

$$F_k(w_t) = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}_k} l_i(w_t; x_i^k) \quad (1)$$

for a given loss function $l_i(\cdot; \cdot)$. Then each client securely compute for E epochs, $w_{t+1}^k \leftarrow w_t^k - \mu g_k$ for a mini-batch size of B , leading to $\frac{E}{B} n_k$ updates for a given learning rate μ . The master FL server finally aggregates the computed model weights as

$$w_{t+1} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k w_{t+1}^k \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_k = n_k/n$ is selected traditionally to reflect averaging on “aggregation”. Despite its utility, the average aggregation method is susceptible to attacks from local malicious parameters. Since the breakdown point of the mean is $1/K$, the presence of a malicious device among the selected devices can cause a notable deviation of the resulting global model from the original average [16].

A. Working Principles

Fig. 1 shows the process of the BCN-based SSI using FL. The main idea of the proposed method is to establish trust between clients (or vehicular users in our scenario) and the aggregation server while keeping the identity and data of clients private, leading to only an unnoticeable delay in convergence. The interaction enables the secure and transparent execution of Machine Learning (ML)-related transactions without the need for a central authority. The process consists of six main phases.

Steps (1-2-3) Registration and authentication: When a vehicle user joins the FL system, the registration phase is needed to authenticate the vehicle user’s identity. In this phase, clients will register their IP addresses to the central/aggregation node that is responsible for the aggregation of model weights. In case of failure, vehicular users will not be allowed to join the FL protocol.

Step-4) Training: In this phase, once the vehicle users are successfully authenticated, clients train their local models. Most of the time, the local training procedure involves running a SGD algorithm, as shown above.

Step-5) Aggregation: Smart contract on BCN (acting similar to aggregation node) performs a weighted averaging of the model to generate the global model of communication round t . The aggregation rule can be in different forms, such as the weighted sum rule ($\alpha_k = n_k/n$) or Byzantine fault-tolerant aggregation rules [16].

Step-6) Global Parameters: The global parameters w_{t+1} are sent back to the clients at the iteration $t + 1$. The whole FL procedure, starting at step 3 is re-executed until the global model converges.

To summarize, our method introduces an innovative approach by integrating BCN-based SSI into the FL framework. This integration directly addresses several critical FL challenges, ensuring enhanced system security and operational integrity.

- **Identity Verification:** In conventional FL systems, it is difficult to authenticate the identity of vehicle users, which is crucial for preventing spoofing and Sybil attacks. The BCN-based SSI uses blockchain technology to maintain a verifiable and immutable record of each vehicle user’s identity. This ensures that each participant in the FL process is authenticated and authorized, preventing unauthorized access and vehicle user in the training process.
- **Node Trustworthiness:** Trustworthiness in FL means ensuring that the vehicle users do not maliciously modify the training data or model updates. The BCN-based SSI framework uses smart contracts on the blockchain to enforce the vehicle user’s rules and verify the integrity of the data shared by the vehicle user. By coding these contracts to automatically validate updates from each node against predefined criteria, our system minimizes the risk of erroneous or malicious updates being injected into the model.

FIGURE 1: THE INTEGRATION OF DID INTO A BLOCKCHAIN NETWORK ALLOWS FL CLIENTS TO INTERACT WITH SMART CONTRACTS.

- **Security and Data Integrity:** Ensuring data integrity while maintaining privacy is of paramount importance in FL. The BCN-based SSI framework helps to secure data through encryption and the tamper-proof architecture inherent in the blockchain. Each transaction on the blockchain is encrypted and linked to previous transactions, creating an immutable chain of data exchange. This not only protects the data against alterations but also creates a clear audit trail that can be used to trace discrepancies back to their source.
- **Decentralized Control Without Compromising Centralized Efficiency:** Our hybrid approach combines the decentralized verification capabilities of BCN-based SSI with a centralized control mechanism that monitors node participation and model updates during the FL process. This leverages the benefits of decentralization, such as reducing the risk of individual failures and improving data privacy, while providing the centralized monitoring necessary to maintain the order and efficiency of the system. This centralized mechanism is critical to quickly identify and mitigate issues such as data tampering or policy violations and ensure that the FL network remains robust against attacks or failures.

Therefore, this synergy of BCN-based SSI with federated learning enables robust identity verification and trustworthiness checking, while effectively managing and excluding malicious actors through a centralized oversight mechanism. Taken together, these measures solve the fundamental trust-

worthiness issues in FL without sacrificing the benefits of decentralized data control, improving both the performance and reliability of the FL system.

B. Neural Network Model Details in FL Phases

The neural network model utilizes the TensorFlow Constrained Optimization (TFCO) library to solve constrained optimization problems during training. This customized model features one hidden layer and uses placeholders for input data \mathbf{X} (input features) and \mathbf{y} (output labels). The hidden layer, comprising $n_classes$ units, employs the `pos_leaky_relu` activation function. A modified version of Leaky ReLU is defined as follows.

$$\text{pos_leaky_relu}(x; \alpha) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x > 0 \\ -\alpha x & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Here, x is the input and α is the trainable parameter. The output of the hidden layer is given by

$$\mathbf{z}_1 = \text{pos_leaky_relu}(\mathbf{X}\mathbf{w}_1 + \mathbf{b}_1) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{X} is the input data of shape $[\text{batch_size}, n_features]$, \mathbf{w}_1 is a weight matrix of size $[n_features, n_classes]$, \mathbf{b}_1 is a bias vector of size $[n_classes]$. The final output layer is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \text{pos_leaky_relu}(\mathbf{z}_1) \quad (5)$$

This FL model predicts the Central Processing Unit (CPU) load of the server based on radio conditions, such as average Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) full-rank usage (see [17] for details).

III. Proposed BCN SSI-enabled Architecture for FL

This section details the novel architecture proposed for integrating SSI with FL and outlines the structure and components of the proposed architecture, explaining how it leverages blockchain and SSI to address the challenges in FL. A promising approach to ensure trust in data exchange between entities (e.g. clients and servers) is the use of DLTs such as blockchain for model management. When model updates are stored in a blockchain ledger, the risk of information misuse is minimized. In FL, for example, reliance on a single centralized FL agent in dynamic and mobile wireless environments can lead to malfunctions and scalability issues [10]. DLTs in FL data exchange can serve as a verifiable mechanism to ensure trust and significantly reduce the potential for information misuse. It is important to note that in this process, only the data intended for transparency and verification is stored in the ledger, while all private data exchanged between entities can remain securely protected by techniques such as selective recording, anonymization, encryption, access control or zero-knowledge proofs. The integration of FL system with DLT can be achieved by a module or layer that interacts with the DLT to store and retrieve FL model updates in a secure and transparent manner. A secure data exchange between FL systems and DLT can be achieved with a secure communication protocol that ensures only the desired data can be stored in the DLT, excluding all private data. Smart contract-based trust verification provides proof of trust through the DLT by verifying the authenticity and integrity of the data exchanged between entities. On the other hand, permissioned DLT can also be utilized to ensure privacy by selecting only authorized entities to access the DLT. Access control mechanisms and encryption techniques can be implemented to protect the data in the DLT to achieve this.

Fig. 2 shows methods of network security and privacy for vehicular users relying on SSI-based BCN solution while performing FL. In a classical BCN-based SSI system that uses FL, the verification of the vehicle user’s credentials during registration and authentication is done by checking the DID in a permissionless blockchain network as shown in Fig. 2(a). This can be done immediately without the need for the issuer’s involvement. Additionally, the vehicle user has the ability to control which attributes are disclosed or kept private during interactions with the FL aggregation server.

Fig. 2(b) is an advancement of Fig. 2(a) and includes the use of another permissionless blockchain network for the permanent and secure recording of other relevant vehicular data. Note that this second BCN provides integrity to each vehicular user’s local training model. When vehicle users

FIGURE 2: SSI ARCHITECTURES WITH FL (A) AUTHENTICATION ONLY, (B) INTEGRITY AND AUTHENTICATION.

participate in FL process, they first verify their digital identities by presenting certificates and attestation to an identity verifier that relies on SSI-based BCN. Note that separate transactions at this stage are needed for each user which can be very time-consuming. Once their identities have been verified, the vehicle users can use the blockchain network to exchange information with FL aggregation server, increasing the reliability and integrity of the system.

The consensus algorithm that is selected has a major impact on the amount of time that blockchain networks consume. Due to mining complexity and network latency,

Proof of Work (PoW), which is utilized by Bitcoin, requires solving intricate puzzles and results in significant energy usage and longer block delays. Since Proof of Stake (PoS) chooses validators based on staked coins, it achieves consensus finality more quickly. PoS is the technology behind Ethereum 2.0 and Cardano. EOS and TRON use a method called Delegated Proof of Stake (DPoS), which elects delegates to validate transactions. This method can decrease block time variability, but it causes delays in the voting process. Hyperledger Fabric employs Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT), which is effective in permissioned environments but requires numerous voting rounds, increasing communication overhead and time consumption. IOTA and Hedera Hashgraph use Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), which confirms transactions asynchronously and usually enables faster confirmations and high transaction throughput with low latency. In order to maximize security and efficiency, hybrid consensus methods incorporate PoW, PoS, and other algorithms; nonetheless, they may cause coordination issues. Block size, transaction fees, node speed, and network scalability are additional elements that affect time consumption. The speed at which blocks are added to the blockchain and transactions are verified is determined by all of these variables combined. To satisfy particular network needs, the trade-offs between security, scalability, and energy efficiency of any consensus method must be carefully considered.

To summarize the novelty of our architecture, it can uniquely integrate BCN-based SSI to enable robust identity verification and trust management in FL. This integration ensures that each participating vehicle is authenticated by an immutable and verifiable blockchain ledger, reducing the risk of identity spoofing and unauthorized access. The combination of decentralized identity management with a centralized control mechanism to monitor node participation is another novelty. This hybrid approach leverages the decentralization benefits of blockchain while ensuring efficient and secure FL operations.

IV. Proposed Registration, Authentication Phases

This section discusses the proposed registration and authentication processes in detail. Section IV.A describes the potential security threats that the proposed system needs to address. Section IV.B explains the use of Elliptic-Curve Cryptography (ECC) in ensuring secure communications. Section IV.C details the process by which a vehicle user registers and is authenticated within the FL system. Section IV.D describes how authenticated users securely join and participate in the FL process. When vehicle users participate in the FL process, they first verify their digital identities by presenting secrets and attestation to an identity verifier using a BCN-based SSI. Therefore, we have proposed an authentication mechanism to verify the legitimacy of the vehicle user and the FL server so that the vehicle user can participate in the FL process securely. This proposed regis-

tration and authentication phase will help prevent malicious vehicle users from participating in the FL process.

A. Threat Models

In the development of the authentication protocol between vehicle users and FL server, the widely used Dolev Yao [18], Canetti-Krawczyk (CK), and extended Canetti-Krawczyk (eCK) adversary [19] are used. According to this model, the adversary can do the following activities

- The adversary can intercept the communication between the vehicle user and the FL server to perform malicious activities.
- The adversary can get the long-term secrets used between the vehicle user and the FL server.
- Any adversary can impersonate the FL server as a legitimate vehicle user.
- The adversary can edit, delete, and resend the messages to the FL server to disrupt the services of the FL server or perform a DoS or replay attack.

B. Elliptic Curve Cryptography

An elliptic curve $E_p(a, b)$ is defined by the equation $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$, where a and b are coefficients, and p is a prime number. This curve is defined over the finite field F_p . Additionally, G represents the subgroup of the additive group of points on $E_p(a, b)$ with order q . These definitions form the basis of ECC, a cryptographic system widely used for secure communication.

The three fundamental mathematical computational problems in ECC are:

- *Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP)*: Given a point p on the curve $E_p(a, b)$ and another point q , find an integer a is impossible from $q = aP$.
- *Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) Problem*: Given points p and q on the curve $E_p(a, b)$, find the shared secret point S such that $S = aP = bq$, where a, b is a secret integer chosen independently by each party.
- *Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA)*: Computing whether cP is equal to abP is indeed infeasible, even if aP , bP , and cP are known.

These mathematical problems form the basis of the security of ECC-based cryptographic systems and are crucial for ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of communications. As we are aware that Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA) cryptographic algorithm is computationally demanding, given that RSA 2048-bit encryption provides a comparable level of security as ECC 256-bit encryption. ECC demonstrates superior efficiency, particularly regarding key size and computational complexity. However, Advanced Encryption System (AES), while lightweight, does not guarantee fully perfect forward secrecy, whereas ECC does offer this feature.

C. Registration Phase

In this phase, the vehicles register their identities with the ID issuer, and the ID issuer shares the generated secrets and stores the vehicle's user information in the BCN-based SSI via the secure channel. Vehicle users use the secrets for identity verification when participating in the FL server. Table 1 lists the notation and their corresponding meanings utilized in the proposed protocol. The following steps show the registration phase:

- The vehicle user selects the identity V_i , the random number K , and the password PW , forwards V_i, K to the ID issuer.
- ID issuer receives the credentials, verify their database, if they exist, then abort otherwise, chooses a prime A , elliptic curve E over a finite field F_A and a point $G \in E$ of order B . It selects the random number P_A and computes the public key $P_B = P_A X$. Afterwards, it saves the V_i and K and forwards the $\langle P_B \rangle$ to the Vehicle user.
- When vehicle user receives the P_B then it computes the $S = E_{PW}(PB, V_i, K)$ into the database.

TABLE 1: NOTATIONS AND MEANINGS

Notations	Description
V_i	Identity of user
PW	Password
E	Elliptic curve
H	Hash Function
E	Encryption
SK	Session Key
E_{PW}	Encryption using PW
K, r_1, r_2	Random numbers
T_1, T_2, T_3	Timestamps
P_A	Private key of ID issuer
P_B	Public Key ID issuer
$R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4, M_1, M_3$	Cryptograms
R_2^*	* Indicates that R_2 is picked up from the database.
v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4	Outputs of hash function

D. Authentication Phase

The authentication phase is carried out between the vehicle user (V_i), Blockchain, and the FL server. During the authentication process, V_i , blockchain, and the FL server participate in verifying the legitimacy of the vehicle user and the FL server. The channel between the blockchain and the vehicle user is taken insecure, while the channel between the blockchain and the FL server has been taken secure. We establish a secure channel between the blockchain and the FL server because we assume that FL has access to the blockchain node containing the information of the vehicle user V_i [20], [21]. Our authentication mechanism for the vehicle user, blockchain, and the FL server is based on the ECC and the hash function.

- V_i participates, then first it inputs the password PW to decrypt S in order to obtain the secrets $\{V_i, K, P_B\}$. V_i chooses a random number r_1 and the timestamp T_1

to compute the $R_1 = r_1 G$ and $R_2 = r_1 P_B$, $M_1 = (V_i, K, T_1, R_1) \oplus H(R_2)$, $H(M_1, R_2, T_1, V_i, K) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$. After computing this, it forwards $\langle v_1, T_1, M_1, R_1 \rangle$ to the blockchain server for verification.

- When the blockchain received $\langle v_1, T_1, M_1, R_1 \rangle$, it selects the timestamp T_2 to verify the obtained message freshness through the verification of $T < T_2 - T_1$. If condition matches then computes the $R_2^* = P_A R_1$ to extract the $(V_i^*, K^*, T_1^*, R_1^*) = M_1 \oplus H(R_2^*)$. Based on the extracted V_i , it extracts the secrets (V_i, K) of the V_i . It then computes $H(M_1, R_2^*, T_1^*, V_i^*, K^*) = v_1^*, v_2^*, v_3^*, v_4^*$ to verify $\{R_2 == R_2^*, V_i == V_i^*, T_1 == T_1^*, R_1 == R_1^*, K == K^*, v_1 == v_1^*\}$. If the received secrets match with the saved, then it is believed that V_i is legitimate and selects random number r_2 to compute $R_3 = r_2 G$, $R_4 = r_2 R_1$, $SK = v_2^* \oplus R_4$, $M_3 = H(v_3, SK, R_2, T_2, T_1)$ and forwards the $\langle M_3, R_3, T_2 \rangle$ to the V_i and $\langle SK, V_i \rangle$ to the FL server.
- When V_i get the $\langle M_3, R_3, T_2 \rangle$, verifies the received message freshness by examining $T = T_3 - T_2$, if it holds then computes $R_4^* = r_1 R_3$, $SK^* = v_2 \oplus R_3^*$ and $M_3 = H(v_3, SK^*, R_2, T_2, T_1)$. Afterwards, it compares $M_3 == M_3^*, T_2 == T_2^*$ to confirm that the blockchain is authentic.
- Conversely, given that the FL server has access to B , it can obtain the SK necessary for communication with V_i .

V. Security Verification of the Authentication Phase

This section evaluates the security of the authentication phase through various verification methods. Section V.A analyzes the security features of the authentication process in an informal manner, covering aspects like mutual authentication and resistance to various attacks. Section V.B conducts a formal analysis of the authentication phase using established security verification tools and methods.

A. Informal Security Verification of the Authentication Phase

This subsection describes how the proposed protocol offers the security features as mentioned in Table 4.

1) Mutual Authentication

When B receives $\langle M_1, v_1, R_1, T_1 \rangle$ from V_i , it proceeds to verify the integrity of the received message using the stored secrets K, V_i, P_A . If the received message satisfies the conditions $R_2 == R_2^*$ and $v_1 == v_1^*$, then B concludes that V_i is authentic, as only V_i possesses the stored secrets required for such verification. Conversely, when V_i receives $\langle M_3, R_3, T_2 \rangle$ from B , it verifies the integrity of the message using its stored secrets K, V_i, P_A . If $M_3 == M_3^*$,

FIGURE 3: THE PROPOSED AUTHENTICATION PHASE

V_i assumes the authenticity of B . These steps elucidate how mutual authentication is established between V_i and B .

2) Resistant against Privacy attack

The exchanged messages $\langle M_1, v_1, R_1, T_1 \rangle$ and $\langle M_3, R_3, T_2 \rangle$ between V_i and B are transmitted in encrypted and hashed form. Consequently, capturing these exchange messages will not reveal the identities of the participating vehicle users. This encryption and hashing process ensures the confidentiality and integrity of the communication, maintaining the anonymity of the involved parties.

3) Perfect Forward Secrecy

The protocol asserts that even if an attacker obtains the long-term secrets, they cannot acquire previous session keys. ECC is employed in the protocol to provide perfect forward secrecy. In the event that an attacker manages to acquire R_3 and R_1 , they are unable to obtain R_2 and R_4 due to the computational hardness of the discrete logarithm problem,

as discussed in the preceding section. Consequently, the proposed protocol guarantees perfect forward secrecy, ensuring that previous session keys remain secure even if long-term secrets are compromised.

4) Resistant against Device-stolen-attack

The protocol emphasizes that even if an attacker manages to obtain the secrets stored on the vehicle device, they still cannot acquire previous session keys. This security is achieved by utilizing random numbers that differ for each session. Consequently, obtaining long-term secrets such as K, V_i, P_A will not facilitate the derivation of previous session keys. Additionally, all previous session keys are derived using ECC, making it challenging for an attacker to obtain these numbers. Therefore, the protocol's design ensures robust security measures against attempts to derive previous session keys, even if secrets stored on vehicle device are compromised.

5) Resistant against Traceable-attack

The protocol emphasizes that even if an attacker obtains messages from different authentication sessions, they cannot link user identity or location. This is achieved by incorporating a random number in every computed secret, making it challenging for the attacker to establish connections between them. For instance, in the message $\langle M_1, v_1, R_1, T_1 \rangle$, all the secrets included in this message utilize a random number that varies for each session. This randomized approach ensures that even if an attacker intercepts multiple messages, they cannot correlate them to deduce user identity or location, thereby enhancing the protocol's security.

6) Resistant against Replay-attack

The protocol ensures that an attacker cannot replay captured old messages as new ones to the communicating entities during authentication. To offer protection against replay attacks, timestamp and random number are included in the exchanged messages between B and V_i . It is assumed that if the clock is synchronized, the timestamp will function effectively. However, if the clock is not synchronized, a random number, acting as a nonce, will be utilized to prevent replay attacks. This dual approach provides robust defense mechanisms against replay attacks, ensuring the integrity and security of the authentication process regardless of clock synchronization.

7) DoS-attack Prevention

As mentioned earlier, the protocol safeguards against replay attacks, preventing an attacker from replaying old messages as new ones. Additionally, the use of timestamps enables the communicating entities to verify the freshness of messages. This feature serves as a defense against attackers attempting to send multiple requests to jam the network. By leveraging timestamps, the receiving entity can discern whether a message is stale or not, thereby mitigating the impact of such malicious activities aimed at disrupting network operations.

8) Resistant against Impersonation Attack

The protocol addresses concerns regarding attackers attempting to create forged messages to impersonate communicating entities. This threat is mitigated by the utilization of long and random numbers in deriving messages within the protocol. Consequently, crafting forged messages to deceive communicating entities becomes exceptionally difficult due to the robustness provided by the protocol's design.

B. Formal Security Verification of the Authentication Phase

This segment delves into the formal security verification of the proposed protocol, ensuring its robust security measures. The security verification of the proposed authentication

mechanism is performed using the formal logic Real-Or-Random (ROR) and validation tool Scyther [22] and Automatic Validation of Internet Security Protocols and Applications (AVISPA) [23]. These simulation tools are used to demonstrate that our proposed protocol can handle different types of attacks mentioned in [24], [25].

1) Formal Security Analysis Using ROR Logic

The Real-Or-Random (ROR) logic serves as a widely recognized approach utilized by security experts to assess the robustness of session keys and secrets shared during mutual authentication protocols. This method revolves around a strategic interaction between two entities, characterized as polynomial-time Turing machines denoted by T . These entities assume the roles of a challenger (C) and an adversary (AT), where AT endeavors to extract confidential information from the messages exchanged via the public channel. Within this framework, C operates within the system where the protocol under scrutiny is employed, while A orchestrates simulated attacks on a real-time system implementing the protocol. It is imperative for C to thwart AT from gaining unfettered access to the system's information. To accomplish this objective, C constructs an oracle system that constrains AT to acquiring only limited information from the system during the interaction. The oracle establishes parameters, introduces a fair coin (CN), and prompts AT to predict the outcome of coin flips within a polynomial time frame using specific inquiries from the model.

The proposed protocol unfolds in two primary phases: In this phase, the vehicles register their identities with the ID issuer, and the ID issuer shares the generated secrets and stores the vehicle's user information in the BCN-based SSI via the secure channel. The authentication phase is carried out between the vehicle user (V_i), Blockchain, and the FL server. During the authentication process, V_i , blockchain, and the FL server participate in verifying the legitimacy of the vehicle user and the FL server. The channel between the blockchain and the vehicle user is taken insecure, while the channel between the blockchain and the FL, server has been taken securely. Since during authentication, data traverses a public channel, rendering it vulnerable to interception by unauthorized or malevolent entities. The entities designated as U , B , are represented as U^i , and B^j , respectively. Since we assume that the channel between the blockchain and FL server is secure, we assume that AT can intercept the communication between U and B . The adversary leverages predetermined inquiries, denoted as (AT), to execute real-time assaults. Additionally, another instance of the adversary denoted as (a) of AT^a , is introduced in the subsequent discussion, with specific inquiries delineated accordingly.

- *Execute (U^i, B^j)* : AT^a instigates this inquiry to intercept the communication transpiring between U^i and B^j amid the authentication process.

- *Reveal* (AT^a): AT^a performs this inquiry with the intention of acquiring the session key generated between U^i and B^j .
- *Test* (AT^a): AT^a executes this inquiry to ascertain the confidentiality of the session key shared between U^i and B^j . In order to assess its secrecy, AT^a flips a coin to predict the outcome using *Test query*.
- *Corrupt queries*: This inquiry is employed to extract the private keys of both U and B engaged in the communication. Its purpose is to demonstrate the perfect forward secrecy of the scheme.
- *Session specific state reveal queries* (AT^a): As per the CK adversary model, the attacker can obtain session-specific state information generated by UE and B respectively. It's important to note that this query does not disclose any long-term private keys of UE or B .
 - $SSReveal(U) = \{r_1\}$.
 - $SSReveal(B) = \{r_2\}$.

Theorem 1: Suppose AT^a endeavors to ascertain the session key (SK) between U^i and B^j during the authentication phase within a polynomial timeframe. Under these circumstances, AT in breaching the authentication process is constrained by $Ad_{AT} \leq \frac{|G_H|^2}{2|F|} + (1 + |G_H|)Ad_{AT}^E$. Here, $|G_H|$ denotes the count of hash queries, $|F|$ represents the range space for the hash function $H(\cdot)$, and Ad_A^E signifies A^a 's advantage in tackling the ECDH problem.

Proof: In proving this theorem, we demonstrate that A^a is incapable of identifying the session during the authentication process. We introduce four games, labeled as G_k , where k ranges from 0 to 3. AT employs these games as part of the ROR logic proof to obtain the session key generated between U^i and B^j . The event S_{ATG_k} , utilized in the proof, is defined as AT^a 's ability to guess the values of c . The probability, denoted as $P[S_{ATG_k}]$, quantifies the competitive advantage of winning the game within the framework of the ROR logic.

Game (G_0): In the initial game, initiated by AT^a to commence the real-time attack on the authentication process, the outcome of the attack's success or failure depends on a random coin toss performed at the beginning of the game. By analyzing the significance of this outcome, we can deduce the effectiveness of the attack as

$$Ad_{AT} = [2P[S_{ATG_0}] - 1]. \quad (6)$$

Game (G_1): Based on the observations from the G_0 , it's evident that AT^a didn't gain any valuable information. Subsequently, AT utilizes the "Execute" query to retrieve the exchanged messages $\{(M_1, v_1, R_2, T_1), (M_3, R_3, T_2)\}$ between U and B during the authentication process. After obtaining these messages, AT^a employs the *Reveal* and *Test* queries in an attempt to deduce the secret session key of the authentication phase, but these efforts prove fruitless. This failure arises from each message containing a unique random number and secrets exchanged in encrypted or hashed form. Due to the hash property, AT^a cannot decipher the random

numbers and other secrets used in the authentication process. Moreover, these secrets are utilized for a short duration and promptly erased from memory.

In summary, it can be concluded that AT^a will not succeed in extracting meaningful data from the first and second games. Therefore, G_0 will be considered equivalent to G_1 i.e.,

$$P[S_{ATG_1}] = P[S_{ATG_0}]. \quad (7)$$

Game(G_2): The outcomes of the first two games indicate that AT cannot discern the secrets utilized in the session key. In this scenario, A^a makes a final attempt by executing the *Test* operation to obtain the random numbers used during the authentication session. Additionally, AT^a utilizes the *Corrupt* query to access the long-term secrets. This is because, during authentication, random numbers are generated using ECC. Due to the inherent complexity of the discrete logarithm problem, acquiring these random numbers becomes exceedingly difficult. Moreover, it is computationally unfeasible to simultaneously acquire both long and short-term keys. The outcome of this concluding game demonstrates that the attacker still cannot deduce the session key of the authentication process, primarily due to the challenges associated with extracting the random numbers obscured by the hash and ECC. Consequently, the probability of winning the final game is comparable to that of the second game. Therefore, based on the principles of the birthday paradox and the computational complexity of the *ECDH* problem, it can be inferred that A^a remains unsuccessful in compromising the security of the session key. In other words, we have

$$P[S_{ATG_1}] - P[S_{ATG_2}] \leq Ad_{AT}^E + \frac{|G_H|^2}{2F}. \quad (8)$$

Game(G_3): In this game, we consider the CK adversary model and assume that either the session state variables or the long-term secret variables are revealed at each involved participant. During this game, AT^a attempts to obtain $\{r_1, r_2\}$ by executing *Execute* and *Hash* queries, along with *SSReveal* and *Corrupt* queries. However, the attacker AT^a fails to derive the required variables $\{r_1, r_2\}$ to compute the session key, as this necessitates knowledge of both the ephemeral and long-term key material of at least UE , HN , and AF . Consequently, for success, AT^a would need to both solve the ECDH problem and execute a successful hash query i.e.,

$$P[S_{AG_2}] - P[S_{AG_3}] \leq |G_H|Ad_A^E \quad (9)$$

After AT^a has played all the games, one might expect that AT^a should have guessed the exact value. Given this context, we can draw the following conclusion.

$$P[S_{ATG_2}] = \frac{1}{2}, \quad (10)$$

following from Equations (6) (7), (8), (9) and (10), we finally obtain

$$\begin{aligned} Ad_{AT} &= [2P[S_{ATG_0}] - 1] \\ &= P[S_{ATG_2}] - P[S_{ATG_3}]. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

We also get the following result from Equations (9) and (11)

$$Ad_{AT} \leq \frac{|G_H|^2}{2F} + (1 + |G_H|)AT_{AT}^E.$$

The outcome of this analysis demonstrates that under the ROR model assumption, AT^a consistently fails to decipher the secrets involved in the authentication process. This strongly suggests that the security of these phases is maintained, and obtaining the session key within polynomial time is impractical.

2) Security Verification Using Scyther Tool

The designed authentication mechanism for the vehicle user and the FL server is validated with the widely used tool Scyther [22]. The scyther tool simulates the authentication protocol using the specification protocol description language (.spdl). It verifies the protocol under the assumptions of the widely used threat models such as DY, CK, and eCK threat models [26]. The security of the authentication mechanism is examined using the four properties Alive, weak agree, Niagree, Nisynch, and secrets [27], [28]. During the simulation of the authentication protocol, three roles are formed: vehicle user role, blockchain role, and FL-server role. Inside the role, all exchanged messages are displayed, and security properties are set for verification. After that, the following settings are made: Perfect Forward Secrecy (PFS), Random Number Leakage, Session Key Reveal, and State Reveal. These settings are made to verify that the authentication mechanism can provide PFS, resistance to ephemera, and session key security. In addition, parameter settings such as verification parameters, advanced parameters, and graph output are specified to measure the robustness of the designed protocol. The simulation result shown in Fig. 4 demonstrates that the designed protocol for the vehicle user and the FL server ensures all the security parameters under simulation settings. This shows that the designed protocol is secure under the above threat model and can handle the attacks.

3) Security Verification Using AVISPA Tool

To verify the security of the developed authentication protocol, we use the AVISPA tool [23]. This tool is based on formal, expressive, and modular language. Moreover, it uses the backend servers using falsification and abstraction-based verification methods for both a finite and an infinite number of sessions. This tool simulates the authentication protocols in the High-Level Protocols Specification Language (HLPSL) to examine the security properties of the designed protocol [29]. The security of the designed protocol is validated using four types of backend servers: (1) On-the-fly Model Checker (OFMC); (2) Constraint Logic-based Attack Searcher (CL-AtSe); (3) SAT-based Model-Checker (SATMC); and (4) Tree Automata based on Automatic Approximations for the Analysis of Security Protocols (TA4SP)

[30]. In general, the security researcher used the OFMC and the CL -Atse backend server to ensure the robustness of the designed authentication protocol [31]. We also simulated the proposed authentication mechanism for the vehicle user and the FL server with the OFMC and the CL -AtSe backend server. Three roles are defined in the simulation: Vehicle User, Blockchain, and the FL server. Within the roles, parameters are defined, and messages are exchanged between the roles. We also describe the environment and the session to define the capabilities of the attacker and the description of the public parameters. Finally, a simulation shows that the proposed protocol is secure and can handle all attacks, as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

VI. Numerical and Performance Evaluation

This section evaluates the proposed architecture's performance through simulations and comparative analysis. Section VI.A presents the results of simulation studies conducted to test the architecture. Section VI.B compares the proposed system's security features, computational cost, communication cost, storage cost, and energy consumption.

A. Simulation Analysis

We implemented a container-based Hyperledger Indy as a DID system on OpenStack. Two virtual machines were created in OpenStack, one running a REST server to generate requests to Hyperledger Indy and the other running the DID system. Hyperledger Indy was used for the DID blockchain, and four DID container nodes were created as DID issuers. For implementing a FL system, the aggregation server and FL clients run in a Docker container. FastAPI was used as REST API, and Docker compose was used to run the clients concurrently.

Table 2 contains average values for various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to the experimental implementation of DID for credential operations to determine their performance. The KPIs include the average time for credential presentation (time taken by a client to present a credential during the verification process), offer (time taken by a client to offer a credential during the credential exchange process), DID communication (DIDcomm) connection creation (time taken by a client to create a DIDcomm connection during the DID exchange process), signing (time taken by a client to sign a DIDcomm message during the DID exchange process), and revocation (time taken by a client to revoke a credential during the revocation process). The numerical values in the table are provided for three different scenarios with 20, 30, and 50 clients. For instance, the average time for credential presentation is approximately 2 milliseconds for all three three client scenarios (20, 30, and 50 clients), whereas the average time for credential offer is approximately 35 milliseconds. The average DIDcomm connection creation time ranges from approximately 44 milliseconds, whereas the average DIDcomm signing time is approximately 5 milliseconds for all three client

Claim				Status	Comments
Vehide_user_FL_server	Vehide_User	Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User	Secret r_1	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User1	Secret v_2	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User2	Secret v_3	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User3	Alive	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User4	Niagree	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User5	Weakagree	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User6	Nisynch	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Vehide_User7	Commit Blockchain,XOR(v_2,r_2)	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
	Blockchain	Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain	Secret r_2	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain1	Secret ECC(r_1,P_B)	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain2	Secret XOR(v_2,r_2)	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain3	Alive	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain4	Niagree	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain5	Weakagree	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,Blockchain6	Nisynch	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
	FL_server	Vehide_user_FL_server,FL_server	Secret XOR(v_2,r_2)	Ok	No attacks within bounds.
		Vehide_user_FL_server,FL_server1	Secret V_j	Ok	No attacks within bounds.

FIGURE 4: SCYTHYR SIMULATION RESULT FOR AUTHENTICATION PHASE

TABLE 2
AVERAGE VALUES OF EXPERIMENTAL DID
IMPLEMENTATION FOR CREDENTIAL OPERATIONS

KPI (time, msec)	20/30/50 Clients
Average credential presentation	≈ 2
Average credential offer	≈ 35
Average DIDcomm connection creation	≈ 44
Average DIDcomm signing	≈ 5
Average DIDcomm revoke credential	≈ 15

scenarios. Finally, the average time to revoke a credential using DIDcomm ranges from approximately 15 milliseconds for all three client scenarios.

Table 3 shows the performance of FL over the number of rounds with respect to the duration (in seconds) and Normalized Mean Square Error (NMSE) values. The number of rounds varies from 1 to 30 until convergence. The number

of clients is varied for each round, with options of 20, 30, or 50. First, as expected, the duration of FL process decreases as the number of rounds increases. For example, for 20 clients, the duration increases from 14.49 seconds in the first round to 344.90 seconds in the 30th round. Second, the NMSE values decrease as the number of rounds increases, which shows the learning and successful model building. For example, for 20 clients, the NMSE decreases from 1.06 in the first round to 0.61 in the 30th round. Third, For a fixed number of rounds, the duration of the FL process is lower for fewer clients. For example, for 20 rounds, the duration increases from 218.17 seconds with 20 clients to 560.40 seconds with 50 clients. Fourth, the NMSE values do not change significantly with the number of clients. Together with Tables 2 and 3, insights into the performance of FL combined with DID systems can be observed in terms of time and accuracy. The FL system results show that it takes a longer time (on the order of

FIGURE 5: AVISPA SIMULATION RESULT FOR AUTHENTICATION PHASE UNDER THE OFMC BACKEND SERVER

TABLE 3
PERFORMANCE WITH FL OVER THE NUMBER OF ROUNDS
VERSUS THE DURATION AND NMSE VALUES

# of Rounds	# of Clients	Duration (s)	NMSE
1	20/30/50	14.49/21.85/36.95	1.06/1.06/1.06
5	20/30/50	33.46/50.78/85.88	0.71/0.71/0.71
10	20/30/50	94.48/144.17/242.19	0.70/0.70/0.69
15	20/30/50	156.01/238.65/400.43	0.68/0.68/0.67
20	20/30/50	218.17/334.13/560.40	0.66/0.66/0.65
25	20/30/50	281.31/430.85/723.02	0.63/0.62/0.61
30	20/30/50	344.90/528.03/886.10	0.61/0.61/0.61

a hundred seconds) as the number of rounds and clients increase, whereas the implemented DID system shows a shorter duration for credential operations.

B. Performance Evaluation

The performance evaluation compares the security features and the cost evaluation in terms of computing power, communication, storage, and energy of the proposed work with the existing protocols for the FL server.

1) Security Feature Comparison

The comparison of the security features demonstrates the comparison of the security of the proposed work with the existing FL-based authentication protocols. When developing the authentication protocol for the vehicle user and the FL server, we take into account the security features specified in [24], [25], [20]. As shown in [20], the authentication protocol [32] is vulnerable to traceable attacks and does not work for decentralization. On the other hand, the method in [20] has some privacy issues [33], [34]. It is also observed that [21] does not protect against impersonation and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. The security assessment conducted in [20] shows that [35] is vulnerable to impersonation, DoS attacks, and does not preserve privacy. Moreover, it does not work in decentralization mode. On the other hand, our proposed protocol for the vehicle user and the FL server provides all the security features (shown in Table 4) mentioned in [24], [25], [20], while [20], [32], [35], [21] fail.

2) Computational Cost

The computational cost section measures the number of cryptographic primitives deployed in the authentication protocol. The cost of the deployed cryptographic operation is estimated with the MIRACL library [36]. Researchers

FIGURE 6: AVISPA SIMULATION RESULT FOR AUTHENTICATION PHASE UNDER THE CL-ATSE BACKEND SERVER

TABLE 4: SECURITY FEATURES COMPARISON OF FL-BASED AUTHENTICATION PROTOCOLS

Protocols	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
[35]	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×
[20]	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[32]	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	✓	✓
[21]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×
Proposed	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Notes: mutual authentication (1), privacy (2), perfect forward secrecy (3), resistant against device-stolen-attack (4), resistant against traceable-attack (5), resistant against de-synchronization attack (6), Decentralization (7), resistant against replay-attack (8), DoS-attack prevention (9), resistant-against impersonation attack (10) Yes-✓, No-×

often use this library to estimate the cost of cryptographic primitives. A testbed experiment is run on the desktop with the configuration Intel-(R) Core(TM) i7-3770 with 3.40 GHz clock frequency, 32 GB RAM, and Linux Ubuntu-18.04.6 LTS to estimate costs [37]. The obtained cost of the cryptographic primitives is used to estimate the cost of the proposed protocol. The description of the cryptographic primitive and the cost obtained through the experiment analysis is shown in Table 5. The proposed protocol requires the $5T_E + 6T_H$ cryptographic primitive during authentication between the vehicle user and the blockchain and FL server. We also estimated

the computational cost for the proposed work and compared it with the other existing FL-based authentication protocols to ensure that our proposal is less expensive than [20], [32], [35], [21] as shown in Table 5. The primary reason for the lower computational cost of the proposed protocol lies in its use of ECC for integrity, whereas other protocols may rely on RSA, pairing, or modular exponentiation, which tend to be more computationally intensive. ECC offers comparable security to RSA and other techniques while requiring smaller key sizes. For instance, ECC with a 256-bit key provides a similar level of security as RSA with a 2048-bit key or

TABLE 5: COMPARISON OF COMPUTATION, COMMUNICATION, STORAGE COSTS, ENERGY CONSUMPTION FOR AUTHENTICATION PROTOCOLS

Protocols	Computational cost (ms)		Communication cost	Storage Cost	Energy Consumption (mj)
	Total operations	Total time (ms)	Total bits	Total bits	Consumption time
[35]	$4T_H + 2T_E + 2T_e + T_P$	9.3	1632	832	53.58
[20]	$4T_E + 4T_H + T_e$	7.01	1600	416	48.9
[32]	$5T_E + 9T_H$	6.83	3168	512	51.2
[21]	$2T_{DH} + 5T_E$	13.9	3104	672	82.44
Our	$5T_E + 6T_H$	6.8	1568	128	50.01

Notes: T_H : Hash function-0.0035 ms, T_E : Scalar Multiplication-1.36 ms, T_P : Billinear pairing-3.45 ms, T_e : Modular exponential-1.56 ms, T_{DH} :DH key exchange-4.2. **Size of Cryptographic primitives:** T_H : 256 bits, T_E -256 bits, T_P -2048 bits, T_e -1024 bits. **Energy required for cryptographic primitives:** T_H -0.00108, T_E -9.8, T_P -15.7, T_e -8.6.

pairing with a 2048-bit size, but with significantly reduced computational overhead.

3) Communication Cost

The communication cost section estimates the number of bits transmitted over the communication channel. The size of the cryptographic operation is used as suggested by the NIST [38]. The authentication protocols has the three messages exchange ($\langle M_1, v_1, R_1, T_1 \rangle$, $\langle M_3, r_3, T_2 \rangle$, $\langle SK, V_i \rangle$) which is 1568 bit. The comparison of communication costs shows that our proposal is lower than [20], [32], [35], [21]. The efficiency of our proposed protocol is further evident in its reduced communication cost, which stems from requiring only three message exchanges compared to other existing protocols that demand more exchanges. Additionally, the exchanged message size is minimized as a result of hashing or utilizing ECC, which typically entails 160 or 256 bits. This stands in stark contrast to protocols relying on RSA or pairing, where the message size can be as large as 2048 bits. Such differences in exchanged message size significantly contribute to the superior efficiency of our proposed protocol compared to existing alternatives.

4) Storage Cost

The storage cost section estimates the vehicle user’s memory requirements for using the secrets to verify identity. The size of cryptographic operations used in memory is equated with the estimated communication cost. The vehicle user stores the S , which is an encrypted message of 128-bit size. The comparison of storage costs shows that our proposed protocol requires much less memory than [20], [32], [35], [21]. In our proposed protocol, the key storage requirement is minimized to 256 bits due to the utilization of ECC. Conversely, in other cases where RSA or pairing is employed, the key size may be larger, typically 2048 bits. This discrepancy in key size further underscores the efficiency of our protocol, as it reduces the storage overhead while maintaining a comparable level of security.

5) Energy Consumption

The energy consumption section estimates the energy required to run the proposed authentication protocol for the vehicle user of the FL server. Energy consumption is estimated similarly to [39]. The energy consumption of the cryptographic operation is shown in Table 5. The proposed protocol requires $0.00066 \times 1568 + 5 \times 9.8 + 6 \times 0.00108$ which is 50.01 mj. The result of the energy consumption shows that our proposal consumes less energy than [32], [35], [21]. However, it takes slightly higher than [20]. Our protocol requires more ECC operations but less hash function than [20], also is more secure than [20]. However, others utilize a combination of modular exponential or pairing, which consumes higher energy compared to ECC.

VII. Discussion of Results

This section discusses the implications of the results obtained from the security and performance evaluations. Section VII.A summarizes the security features verified in the proposed system. Section VII.B explores the privacy implications of the proposed architecture, ensuring that the privacy of participants is maintained.

A. Security Features

We see that our proposed protocol provides more security for the vehicle user and the FL server than [20], [32], [35], [21]. In terms of performance, the proposed protocol also performed better than [20], [32], [35], [21] in terms of computational, communication, storage, and energy consumption. The proposed protocol reduces computational cost to 26.8%, 2.9%, 0.4%, 51%, communication cost to 3%, 2%, 50%, 49%, storage cost to 84%, 69%, 75%, 80% and energy consumption to 6%, 2%, 3.9% than [20], [32], [35], [21]. Therefore, the outcome of the security comparison and performance evaluation shows that the proposed protocol performs better than [20], [32], [35], [21].

B. Potential Privacy Implications

To address the privacy implications of the proposed approach, careful design of the FL system in the context of a BCN-based SSI solution may be required. With FL, data

is collected and used for model training by multiple participants, often on different Edge devices or nodes. This can lead to concerns about data sharing and potential disclosure of sensitive information during the training process. In a BCN-based SSI system, individuals have control over their data and where it is stored. However, in FL, data is shared among multiple participants, which may not be consistent with individuals' preferences for data residency and sovereignty. In FL, individual data are often anonymized or aggregated to protect privacy. However, there is a risk that aggregating data across participants could lead to re-identification attacks or inferences about sensitive information. In BCN-based SSI, unlinkability of identities is critical for privacy protection. However, in FL, data from multiple identities can be used to train models, leading to linking data to specific identities.

FL systems may also be vulnerable to adversarial attacks, where malicious participants try to infer sensitive information from the shared models. These attacks could compromise the participants' privacy and undermine the confidentiality of the FL process. Additionally, the federated averaging process requires transmitting model updates between participants. These updates may contain information about local data, raising concerns about the exposure of sensitive information during the aggregation process. Individuals have explicit consent and control over their data in an BCN-based SSI system. However, in FL, the degree of control may vary, and participants may not fully see how their data is used or aggregated. Data consistency between nodes is critical for trust in a BCN-based SSI system. However, in FL, data inconsistencies between different nodes can compromise the integrity and reliability of the shared models. In addition, access to training data in FL is limited, making it difficult to conduct transparent audits and inspections to ensure compliance with privacy policies and regulations.

To protect the privacy of vehicles, they can use pseudonymous identities on the blockchain to ensure that their participation is authenticated but their actual identity remains secret. The blockchain only stores anonymized data or cryptographic proofs that verify the validity of transactions without revealing sensitive information. In addition, the data exchanged by vehicles during FL training can be encrypted and only metadata or hashes are stored on the blockchain. This ensures that private data remains secure and does not end up in the public ledger. Vehicles can be selected to participate in FL iterations based on a privacy-preserving algorithm that uses verifiable random functions or zero-knowledge proofs. This ensures that the selection process is transparent and verifiable without jeopardizing the privacy of participating vehicles. The system can also enable dynamic participation, where vehicles can securely join or leave the FL process without revealing their private information. The blockchain records proof of participation and model updates while ensuring that the actual data exchange remains private and secure.

Techniques such as differential privacy, secure aggregation, and secure multiparty computation can enhance privacy protection during the FL process. Moreover, post-quantum cryptography secures the processes against attacks generated from quantum computers [40]. In addition, clear data governance policies, user consent mechanisms, and privacy compliance are critical to maintaining privacy and trust in the integration of FL and BCN-based SSI. On the other hand, regular data protection assessments and audits are essential to ensure compliance and identify potential data protection risks or vulnerabilities. Overall, privacy is a fundamental role in the development and implementation of the combined BCN-based SSI and FL system.

VIII. Conclusions and Future Work

DIM and FL fields offer diverse opportunities, paving the way for getting control over the usage of shared and not-shared data with third parties. In this paper, we considered two different architectural options to provide either only authentication or both authentication and integrity to FL process. We proposed a secure registration and authentication mechanism to verify the legitimacy of the vehicle user and the FL server so that the vehicle user can securely participate in the FL process. We also built an experimental platform where container-based Hyperledger Indy as a DID system on OpenStack, with four DID container nodes created as DID issuers and an FL system with aggregation server and FL clients running in one Docker container using FastAPI as the REST API. Based on the experimental findings, it can be inferred that the integration of blockchain-based credential management of SSI system with the proposed FL-based approach can enhance security and efficiency to a considerable extent.

This study focused on a specific use case of FL for vehicle users, but the proposed approach could be applied to other areas and applications. This may include conducting experiments in different contexts, comparing the performance of the FL approach with alternative methods (e.g., using the potential for transfer learning and gaining insights from one domain to apply FL in related or similar contexts), and considering domain-specific challenges and requirements. Customization and optimization of FL mechanisms are also essential to achieve the best results while maintaining data privacy and security in diverse domains. In the future, exploring additional blockchain-based solutions and security measures (e.g., more sophisticated consensus mechanisms for decentralized trust management and the integration of smart contracts to automatically enforce security policies and trust assessments) that can further improve the trust and integrity of the FL ecosystem is of interest.

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